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MKTG 368-001
Qualitative Research Write-Up
November 30, 2021

DraughtMaster System Qualitative Research Report

Introduction

With more attention drawn to climate change in recent years, many companies have been making the move to greener resource use through recycling and renewable energy options. One of the world's largest beer companies, Carlsberg Group, have implemented their own initiative to reduce their environmental impact. They came up with the Draughtmaster, which alters the traditional beer delivery system by replacing metal kegs with plastic kegs and utilizing the circular economy system. This system not only reduces environmental impact but also provides organizational efficiency. Benefits of this system include: easier handling of kegs because of the decreased size and weight by being plastic rather than metal, being able to recycle the plastic which reduces waste involved with cleaning traditional kegs, and preserving the quality of beer for a longer period of time due to lack of CO2 emissions. Carlsberg has launched this system in Germany and other European countries and is looking to see if it is a viable system that could be adopted by customers in the United States. Through a series of interviews with B2C customers and B2B customers, we have gathered general opinions and thoughts on sustainability in general and in regards to Carlsberg's new Draughtmaster system.

Methodology

In order to gather opinions on the Carlsberg DraughtMaster System, we felt that it was most appropriate to conduct interviews. With an interview, it would allow for us to gauge opinions on the new system, as well as on sustainability as a whole. Interviewing two individuals was the most optimal way for us to gather qualitative research.

The first step in conducting the research was to segment our different audiences. For simplicity purposes, we chose to divide our findings into two: B2B and B2C. We felt that this division was the best way to fully understand our findings and gauge the opinions of a wider audience. It also best suited the industry. In the beer industry, consumption is both by the individual (consumer) and by groupings (business). Since beer can be purchased and consumed in both settings, we thought that it would affect findings. Thus, we chose these two segments.

The next step was to write the interview questions. Starting with the B2C interview, it was needed to first understand the individual. The first set of interview questions revolved on who the individual was. Questions that were asked related to age, occupation, hometown, and major (if they were a student). With these baseline questions, we could get a foundation and an understanding of who the consumer was outside of the interview setting. It was also beneficial to gather this information for segmentation purposes. For example, if multiple B2C interviews are conducted, it is important to draw the pattern between sustainability attitudes among students,

professionals, elders, etc. These demographics paint a better picture on how the general audience would respond to the DraughtMaster System.

After these initial questions, we then asked what the individual's sustainability habits were. Again, it provided background context that would help understand their attitudes to the Carlsberg system. Once that understanding was established, we transitioned to asking about attitudes towards sustainability in the beer industry, then to introducing the DraughtMaster System. When introducing the new system, we made sure that we gave all the information we had. We included an educational video that explained and visualized how the new system worked. From there, the individual was able to gauge how they felt about the new system.

The B2B interview was outlined in a very similar fashion. We started with gathering background information: what kind of business it was, how long it had been established, location, and general demographics of usual customers. Afterwards, we followed the same pattern as the B2C interview. We gathered data on the overall attitude towards sustainability, then transitioned to the role sustainability plays in the beer industry, and then finished with the DraughtMaster System. Questions in this interview were more pointed to shipping and delivery, as it is a very relevant part of running a business. Other questions included storage, recyclability, and how it affects price.

Overall, conducting a B2B and B2C interview was the best method to gather qualitative data. In conjunction with a recording of the interview, we were able to go back, draft a transcript, and use the transcript to begin analyzing findings.

Findings

Our interviewees for both our business to consumer and business to business interviews were residents of the US which is notable because of how those in Berlin's answers differed. The most obvious issue that surfaced while conducting the interviews is the lack of the overriding information needed by not only the consumers but the business as well. While many businesses were intrigued in the idea of the DraughtMaster System, they were skeptical of the added costs that seemed to be neglected by Carlsberg. "Potentially? Sure. I don't see why not. I don't see it having any negative effects. But it would really just mainly be if it fit into our system. And you know, the cost of that is the main thing." White dog beverage manager, Glen, when introduced to the DraughtMaster System was intrigued in what the system could potentially do to help aid the environment but was unsure of how this switch would help them save money, especially during such a difficult time like the Covid-19 Pandemic. Many businesses have already established relationships with local vendors as well as a system for recycling the kegs along and delivering them with a specific space set aside for them. Making these changes for a system that is not yet proven to do well with customers is a big risk considering all the added costs.

Along with the concern and risk of the added costs, consumers and business owners are skeptical of how the beer may taste in comparison to the beer in a traditional keg. Many are turned off by the word plastic in today's society because of how we have been conditioned to associate plastic with negative connotations. Carlsberg does have a great vision in what could be but he lacks key

communication with customers of how the beer even holds up against the already established and loved keg system. We are talking about changing decades long of a system that works and in doing that there has to be a way to give complete confidence to those changing the system that the taste would hold up the same. This would go along with the earlier risk of added cost if the taste does not hold up the same and a business loses consumers because of it.

As mentioned earlier, our society is moving towards a plastic free life in order to help aid our environment that has been so negatively impacted by the material. When bringing up sustainability to business owners and consumers, plastic is the last word they thought they would hear in the same sentence. “I really don’t understand one aspect of this. Nowadays we are trying to distance ourselves from plastic, plastic straws are banned and now we want to exchange the barrel for plastic too? For me, this is not a particularly original path. Just why? Doesn’t make sense to me.” This quote alone demonstrates how confused those are of what the system is and how it would benefit the environment. There are even some doubts that the CO2 emissions are less because of the machines needed for the recycling process as well as the production of plastic in the first place. Generally there is a lot of hesitation towards the system and more specifically the installation of said system, due to the fact that it involves the use of plastic. There is also a lack of information or long term research completed to help determine if this system is performing and delivering what Carlsberg says and to the point that can convince business owners to switch their system confidently.

Recommendations

Based on these findings from the research completed by all ten groups, recommendations can be made in relation to Carlsberg's strategy for expansion of the DraughtMaster system into the United States market. Since much of the skepticism that businesses and consumers had surrounding the DraughtMaster related to how well it would replace the traditional metal keg system, how it would affect the quality of the beer, and how sustainable the use of plastic is, the three following recommendations serve to resolve these key issues which may present obstacles to expansion into the U.S. market.

The first recommendation is for Carlsberg to provide guidelines for how the DraughtMaster system can be easily adopted by businesses, and an explanation of the benefits that come with replacing a traditional keg system with the DraughtMaster. From the B2B research it was found that many businesses were skeptical about the costs of replacing their current systems as well as the long term costs of maintenance. One of the research participants, a manager from Quakertown, PA, stated that most bars and restaurants “have keg rooms that they've already spent all of this money on creating,” and that the cost of bringing in a whole new system is a big risk. In order to address these concerns, Carlsberg needs to provide businesses with a clear long-term maintenance price comparison between the DraughtMaster and a traditional keg system. Included in this would be a cost estimate for the implementation of the DraughtMaster. This will be useful in getting businesses to switch to the DraughtMaster if it is shown that it can save money over time, and it also should not be a large cost for Carlsberg to conduct the price comparison.

The second recommendation is for Carlsberg to emphasize how the quality of the beer is unaltered by the DraughtMaster system and the use of plastic kegs. Several of the participants expressed concern regarding how the taste or quality of the beer may be affected by being stored in plastic, and confusion surrounding how the beer maintains its carbonation with a lack of CO₂. When proposing the DraughtMaster to businesses and consumers, Carlsberg needs to prove that the system does not affect the quality of the beer. One way of doing this would be to allow businesses a tasting trial of the DraughtMaster in which they can try the beer from the plastic keg and compare it to normal draft beer. A beverage director based in Philadelphia stated that being able to try the beer first would give him a better idea of how likely they would be to implement the DraughtMaster. While Carlsberg will have to account for the cost of giving out free trials or samples of the beer, it will be worth it in order to gain the trust of businesses.

Lastly, Carlsberg needs to obtain more long-term research on the environmental impact of the plastic keg system, and then clearly explain the findings to consumers through the use of advertising. Skepticism surrounding the use of plastic kegs was one of the biggest issues shown in the research. Since many businesses are working towards limiting the use of plastic within their work for environmental reasons, it seemed counterintuitive to many businesses and consumers to suggest switching to a plastic keg design in order to be more sustainable. When asked about the use of plastic, one participant stated, "Plastic is difficult to recycle, and the kegs are not reusable. I don't feel comfortable. It also depends if the plastic is really recycled." Though there is a baseline explanation for why the plastic keg is environmentally friendly in the sense that it saves water, can be recycled, and limits CO₂ emissions, the widespread distaste for plastic will be a challenging hurdle to overcome. Therefore, Carlsberg must devote more focus to clearly explaining to consumers and businesses how the use of plastic is beneficial in the DraughtMaster system. First, there needs to be a clear comparison showing the environmental impact of a traditional keg to the plastic keg. For example, a big question which came up was if recycling the plastic kegs has a better environmental impact than reusing metal kegs. This information needs to be put in a format that will be easy for consumers to understand, such as in an infographic or an advertisement. Secondly, provide a simple explanation for how plastic can be sustainable, and what the long term impact of the kegs will be on the environment. Lastly, there needs to be more information on the recycling process of the plastic kegs. Many businesses were wondering if there would be any protocol to ensure that they really get recycled rather than just thrown away. The overall cost for this will have to account for the additional research into plastic sustainability and recycling, as well as the creation of materials to relay the information to consumers.

Conclusion

The DraughtMaster presents an innovative solution to the issue of making the draft beer industry more sustainable, however in order to incorporate the new system into the United States Carlsberg must overcome the main concerns of businesses and consumers such as how to implement it, the quality of the beer, and the perception of plastic. This can all be overcome by adopting the correlating recommendations, including providing more explanation of the system, allowing for trials before implementation of the DraughtMaster, and conducting more long-term research on sustainability comparisons to inform possible consumers. Once all these steps are taken, the DraughtMaster should be successful in the United States.